

Project Data Management Plan

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Abstract

This document describes the data management life cycle for the data collected, processed and generated by the ExPaNDS project. Like all Horizon 2020 projects, the first version of this DMP was submitted by month 6 of the project. This updated version delivers the latest snapshot of the project's data management implementation.

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Executive Summary

One of ExPaNDS's main objectives is to promote FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) data in national Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructures (PaN RIs), notably by harmonising and generalising the use of DMPs for experiments carried out in the facilities. ExPaNDS also takes part in the Open Research Data Pilot, which aims to make the research data generated by H2020 projects accessible with as few restrictions as possible, while at the same time protecting sensitive data from inappropriate access.

The way we deal with the project's data must then be an example of FAIRness and openness. That is why we plan to publish all our deliverables in the ExPaNDS community created on Zenodo, to publish our code in GitHub and to present our reference workflows in the PaN training catalogue.

Survey and personal data, which are the only sensitive data in ExPaNDS, are recorded in a private SharePoint environment only accessible to project members.

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1. Introduction

A Data Management Plan is a key element of good data management as it is the initial tool to implement our FAIR data policy.

After a summary of the data collected and generated in the project in chapter 2, how the FAIR principles are applied to ExPaNDS data is described in chapter 3. Then, the DMP addresses resources, security and ethics.

This document follows the EC – H2020 FAIR DMP template provided in the EC portal¹.

¹

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/data-management_en.htm

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2. Data summary

ExPaNDS provides services for scientists who produce or process scientific data. It generates documents (text, presentation, video), websites, demonstrators and source code. It also re-uses existing data sets for analysis but does not generate scientific data like instruments do.

Table 1: Generated and collected data in ExPaNDS

Data type	Origin	Expected size	Contents
Text documents	PC, collaboration space, online document editor	100s Megabytes	Deliverables, meeting minutes, documentation
Presentations	PC, collaboration space, online document editor	100s Megabytes	Training material, dissemination material, presentations at conferences
Videos	PC	100s Megabytes	Training material, dissemination material
Metadata schemas & example files	GitHub, NeXus Format	10s Megabytes	Adopted ontologies for the metadata catalogues
Source code	GitHub, several ExPaNDS facilities	10s Megabytes	Extension & integration of existing catalogues and services
Re-used data sets	Several ExPaNDS facilities	10s Gigabytes	Reference data sets for analysis services to be implemented in EOSC

In the case of existing data sets being re-used, the data policy and the infrastructure of the hosting partner facility are complied with.

Concerning the software, most ExPaNDS developments are extending the functionality of existing software, for which the pre-existing licences are complied with.

The documents, metadata schemas and source code produced by ExPaNDS are mostly useful to data managers, instrument scientists and research software engineers working at national PaN RIs and ESFRIs, providing them with a framework to make their data and processes more FAIR.

3. FAIR Data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The naming convention for the project documents is defined in the project's Quality Assurance Plan².

All public deliverables of the project are uploaded to Zenodo and thus assigned a DOI and automatically harvested by the EOSC search portal³. Once approved by the European Commission, all ExPaNDS results are also findable in CORDIS⁴. The PaN techniques ontology developed as part of the project is registered in community ontology catalogues⁵. The reference data sets and associated analysis workflows are findable as integrated assets in the PaN training catalogue⁶. The reference data sets all have DOIs, either provided by the facility which created them or by Zenodo.

In order to allow detailed tracking of data produced in ExPaNDS, we applied versioning of all entities as follows:

- The project documents get version numbers, as described in the project's Quality Assurance Plan.
- The versioning of the reference data sets follows the data policy of hosting facilities.
- The different versions of the ontologies and source code are managed through GitHub releases.

Making the data produced at national PaN RIs findable by user communities in EOSC was one of the main objectives of ExPaNDS. The project enabled several facilities to publish an OAI-PMH endpoint for their open data to be harvested by e.g. B2FIND⁷ and a PaN search API endpoint for their open data to be harvested in the PaNOSC data portal⁸ with richer metadata. A few data repositories are or are in the process of being also onboarded as EOSC data sources⁹.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

All public ExPaNDS deliverables are openly accessible in Zenodo. The access to confidential deliverables is provided by the SharePoint collaboration space through nominative accounts for project participants. Only a few deliverables are not public because they contain sensitive data (Collaboration Agreement, ethics and human resources allocation).

Anonymous access to public deliverables is guaranteed. For confidential deliverables, the identity is ascertained using SharePoint's credentials.

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4457914>

³ <https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/all?q=expands>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/857641/results>

⁵ <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/PANET>

⁶ <https://pan-training.eu/workflows>

⁷ <https://b2find.eudat.eu/organization/>

⁸ <https://data.panosc.eu/>

⁹ https://search.eosc-portal.eu/search/data-source?q=*

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The re-used reference data sets are available in the contributing RI's repository and accessible through their specific data transfer services.

3.3. Making data interoperable

Only widely used or open-source software is needed to read and modify the project documents (e.g. PDF, MS suite, LibreOffice suite). The code source, Git tool set and software catalogue are written in standard and widespread languages.

Training and documentation on how to apply the ExPaNDS software on our reference data sets are provided as part of the ExPaNDS deliverables¹⁰ and as detailed training workflows in the PaN training catalogue¹¹.

The development of a metadata framework for PaN scientists¹² was one of the objectives of the project, making data produced by our facilities more interoperable in the future. Moreover, more ExPaNDS partners are now part of the Nexus International Advisory Committee (NIAC, www.nexusformat.org/NIAC), carrying on the advocacy for a large adoption of the Nexus data format for PaN data.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

The use of Creative Commons licences BY 4.0 for all public project deliverables is implemented. Concerning the source code for software development and PaN training catalogue, BSD 3-Clause, Apache 2.0 or GPL-3.0 licences were used, depending on the overarching project licensing approach.

The public deliverables were made available as soon as they were submitted to the EU portal, with an extra mention "This deliverable is not yet approved by the European Commission" that was removed once the deliverable was approved. There is no restriction on the re-use of the project's public deliverables after the end of the project.

ExPaNDS data quality assurance processes are described in a dedicated document "Quality Assurance Plan"¹³.

4. Allocation of resources

Zenodo is hosted by CERN and receives long-term funding from CERN, the European Commission and other foundations¹⁴. GitHub is financed through sponsorship and with premium subscription plans for private companies. It is free to use for individuals and academia. Human resources dedicated to FAIR in ExPaNDS were included in its Grant.

WP leaders were responsible for the data management of their own products, with WP1 ensuring the overall compliance of the project to this DMP.

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7417726>

¹¹ <https://pan-training.eu/workflows>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6821676>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4457914>

¹⁴ <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>

Sustainability sheets were created for each of the main outcomes of the project, detailing long-term maintenance and adoption plans for what was developed. These can be found in ExPaNDS Zenodo community¹⁵. During the second phase of ExPaNDS, there was an effort to advocate for the establishment of permanent data steward positions at each of our partner facilities, as well as in LEAPS and LENS as a whole. This effort has already been rewarded with some success.

5. Data security

Data security for all documents and data sets uploaded to Zenodo relies on Zenodo's security measures. Data security for confidential deliverables relies on SharePoint and the Diamond infrastructure.

The reference data sets benefit from the 10 years guaranteed availability of their hosting facility.

Ontologies and code rely on GitHub.com infrastructure.

6. Ethical aspects

The handling of the Protection of Personal Data (POPD) requirements in ExPaNDS is described in a dedicated confidential deliverable (D7.1).

Surveys have been made in the framework of ExPaNDS. Personal data collected for them were deleted after anonymisation or aggregation. Other personal data, like the project's "who's who" document or the list of attendees to training, workshops and conference events, are stored in the collaboration space with restricted access to the project's contributors.

Consent was obtained before any public dissemination of presentations and photos.

¹⁵ <https://zenodo.org/communities/expands/>

